

**A STUDY ON IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG
STUDENTS WITH REFERENCE IN DHANALAKSHMI
SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS),
PERAMBALUR**

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Cite This Article: M. S. Girish, T. Sushena Sruthi & C. Subhashini, "A Study on Impact of Social Media Among Students With Reference in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur", International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 66-70, 2023.

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of social media on among students with reference in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College Perambalur. In this study, analysing the actual impact of daily use of students in social media. Descriptive research design was utilized to gain accurate profile of situation. Sixty (300) Undergraduate & post graduate students who are actively using social media are the respondents of the study. It was conducted during the summer semester of academic year 2019-2020. Summing-up, social networks becomes an integral part of the students' full life, took up most of their free time. Undoubtedly, in social networks, there are also things useful for the development of the students.

Key Words: Social Media, You Tube, Face Book, Google, Twitter, Students.

Introduction:

Social media is an internet-based form of communication. Social media platforms allow users to have conversations, share information and create web content. There are many forms of social media, including blogs, micro-blogs, wikis, social networking sites, photo-sharing sites, instant messaging, video-sharing sites, podcasts, widgets, virtual worlds, and more. Billions of people around the world use social media to share information and make connections. On a personal level, social media allows you to communicate with friends and family, learn new things, develop your interests, and be entertained. On a professional level, you can use social media to broaden your knowledge in a particular field and build your professional network by connecting with other professionals in your industry. At the company level, social media allows you to have a conversation with your audience, gain customer feedback, and elevate your brand.

Only university employees who are authorized by their departments may use social networking to conduct university business. Before you decide if you will make an account, review what other USF departments are doing by looking through the USF Social Media Directory. Also, make sure that your department does not already have a social media account on the sites you plan to use. If an account has already been created, do not create another one. Instead, contact the current account manager if you wish to add content.

Statement of the Problem:

Student's preferences to World Wide Web even the main theme of Social media. They are expressing key problem of Media information taken from sources of various step. It is the draw back from lack of communication to download and technical level. The want of student carefully studied by the condition survey on student's satisfaction.

The study also helps to know various information gathered / collected from the Social media. The study also influences using the website among the students. So students are faced many problems like lack communication, awareness about internet, huge areas of network etc.

Review of Literature:

Charlene Sorensen (2009), this exploratory study assesses the differences and similarities between how instruction librarians in Western Canada use Media and how they instruct students to use it. Survey results indicate that these librarians do use Media but can be influenced by faculty to present Media negatively to students.

Erin Dorris Cassidy et al (2010), this study serves as an update to a previous study by Sam Houston State University librarians about the use and preferences of Internet, communication, and educational technologies among students. Since the previous study was initiated in 2010, the iPad has made its debut and significantly altered the educational technology landscape. In this new landscape, this study investigates student usage of such technologies as instant messaging, cell phones, e-readers, social networking, RSS feeds, podcasts, and tablets. In addition, this study aims to determine which technologies students prefer the library to utilize for

a variety of services, such as reference assistance or book renewals, and which technologies may not be worth the investment, such as geosocial networking.

Wen-Chih Chioued all (2011), Many studies have proposed new website evaluation frameworks and criteria. We have attempted to understand and improve website evaluation through the analysis of 83 articles by classifying them into IS, marketing, and combined-approaches. Our findings showed that most early studies adopted the IS-approach but that later ones (after the burst of the dot-com bubble) shifted to a combined-approach. Our study also revealed that most papers analyzed the evaluation factors via a ranking list. Our review showed that most studies conducted user-based surveys to examine a website, but that very few addressed strategic issues of website evaluation.

Scope of the Study:

The study only helps to identify the student's satisfaction on social media. This study applicable only on Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College. The scope of the study analysis of social media and network which ever analysis of all level of information. The study was conducted to assess the impact of social media on students' academic performance. Three hundred (300) students who are actively using social media are the respondents of the study. It was conducted during the summer semester of academic year 2020. The study limited only on variables of social media that assumed that has effects of respondents' academic performance. These variables are respondents' access to internet, usage, perception on social media, and their frequency of using it.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the different form of media resources.
- To analysis about social media available for convenient to college students.
- To study about various problems faced by the students from social media.
- To give suitable suggestion after analysis of data.

Research Methodology:

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular topic, subject or area of investigation, backed by collection, compilation, Presentation and interpretation of relevant details or data. It is careful search or find out valuation facts, which would be useful for further application or utilization.

Research Design:

The researcher used Descriptive Research Design. Descriptive Research design means fact finding one. The Research used this research design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about student empowerment.

Sampling Design:

The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves deliberating selection of particular units constituting a sample, which represents the universe, is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

Sample size denotes the number of sample selected for the study. They sample size for this study is fixed at 330 respondents.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of data gives statistics of importance of study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data

Primary Data:

Primary Data were collected through Questionnaire. The data which are collected as fresh for the first time and happen to be original in character.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Research Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H0):

Null Hypothesis is formulated only to test whether there is any relationship between variables related to the problem being studied. Usually the null hypothesis usually is formed as a negative statement.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1):

Alternate Hypothesis (H1) is a statement, which is accepted after the null hypothesis is rejected based on the test result. The alternate hypothesis usually is formed as a positive statement.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study only selected for 300 respondents.
- The study on college students for Engineering College students only.

- Time is major constraints for collect the data.
- The study conducted only on limited period.
- Lack of availability of secondary data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Which Social Media Using

S.No	Social Media	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Facebook	99	33%
2	Snap shot	12	4%
3	Instagram	102	34%
4	Pinterest	27	9%
5	Other	60	20%
	Total	300	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above table shows that, 33% of the respondent of the respondents are social media using on Facebook, 4% of the respondent of the respondents are social media using on snap shot, 34% of the respondent of the respondents are social media using on Instagram, 9% of the respondent of the respondents are social media using pinterest, and 20% of the respondent of the respondents are social media using on Facebook. Majority 33% of the respondent of the respondents are social media using on Facebook.

Which Social Media Using:

Correlation:

The table shows the relationship between which social media using and personal benefit using social media.

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
99	18	9,801	324	1,782
12	102	144	10,404	1,224
102	135	10,404	18,225	13,770
27	39	729	1521	1,053
$\sum x = 300$	$\sum y = 300$	$\sum x^2 = 24,678$	$\sum y^2 = 30,510$	$\sum XY = 18,189$

Inference:

This is positive correlation. There is relationship between which social media using and personal benefit using social media.

Testing of Hypothesis:

Chi - Square:

The table shows the analysis of the relationship between Hours a day do you spend on Social Media and consider yourself Addicted to Social Media.

Spend / Social Media Addicted	Less Than 1 Hr	1-2 Hr	3-4 Hr	4-5 Hr	5 + Hr	Total
Yes	11	16	8	4	6	45
No	18	28	15	6	11	78

Sometimes	27	43	22	9	16	117
Neutral	10	16	8	4	6	45
None	3	5	3	1	3	15
Total	69	108	57	24	42	300

(Source: Primary Data)

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significance relationship between spends and social media addicted.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1):

There is a significance relationship between Hours a day do you spend on Social Media and consider yourself Addicted to Social Media.

Degree of Freedom:

Particulars	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
R ₁ C ₁	11	10.3	0.49	0.047
R ₁ C ₂	16	16.2	0.04	0.002
R ₁ C ₃	8	8.5	0.25	0.029
R ₁ C ₄	4	3.6	0.16	0.044
R ₁ C ₅	6	6.3	0.09	0.014
R ₂ C ₁	18	17.5	0.25	0.014
R ₂ C ₂	28	28	0	0
R ₂ C ₃	15	15.5	0.25	0.016
R ₂ C ₄	6	6.2	0.09	0.014
R ₂ C ₅	11	10.5	0.25	0.023
R ₃ C ₁	27	26.5	0.25	0.009
R ₃ C ₂	43	42.1	0.81	0.01
R ₃ C ₃	22	22	0	0
R ₃ C ₄	9	9	0	0
R ₃ C ₅	16	16	0	0
R ₄ C ₁	10	10.5	0.25	0.023
R ₄ C ₂	16	16	0	0
R ₄ C ₃	8	8.5	0.25	0.029
R ₄ C ₄	4	3.6	0.16	0.044
R ₄ C ₅	6	6.3	0.09	0.014
R ₅ C ₁	3	3.4	0.16	0.047
R ₅ C ₂	5	5.4	0.16	0.029
R ₅ C ₃	3	2.8	0.04	0.014
R ₅ C ₄	1	1.2	0.04	0.033
R ₅ C ₅	3	2.1	0.81	0.389
Calculated value				0.827

Level of Significance : 5%
 Table value : 0.827
 Calculate value : 0.818 and consider yourself addicted to Social Media.

Result:

Since the calculated value is less than the table value. So we accept the null hypothesis. There is relationship between Hours a day do you spend on Social Media and consider yourself addicted to Social Media.

Suggestions:

- The Social media facility can be easy communicated with more.
- The Network is technical model expectation in Social media
- Most of the respondents are awareness from Social media facility.
- Most of the respondent's usage for especially student.
- The public must be awareness from Social media for faced some problem.

Conclusion:

From the research I came to know about the important conclusion regarding the student impact of Social Media Based on the findings, social media becomes an integral part of the student's full life, took up most of his spare time. The time spend by the respondents on social media stressed that the impact on their academic performance ends up negative. So, the social media, which also has a familiar name as a social networks or web, chooses.

References:

- Kothari C.R., Research Methodology, K.K. Gupta for New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi, 1985.
- Arun Monoppa, Mirzas Saiyadain, Personnel Management, Tada MC GRAW-HILL Publishing company Ltd.
- David S. Rubin., Statistics for Management, Prentice Hall of India private Ltd, New Delhi.
- Richard M. Hodgetts, Modern Human relations at work, The Dryden Press, USA.
- Tripathi P.C., Personnel Management, Sultan and Chands Company Ltd.